

QUALIFICATIONS FOR STRENGTH: TENSILE PROPERTIES OF BACTERIAL CELLULOSE NANOPAPERS

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ABSTRACT

Nanosized cellulose has recently established itself as a promising material to be used as reinforcement in the production of high performance renewable composite materials. Bacterial cellulose (BC), i.e., nanofibres synthesized by bacteria, such from the *Acetobacter* species, consists of long threads of pure cellulose with a fibre diameter of 50 nm and several micrometres in length. When a continuous network is prepared from BC nanofibres or other nanocellulosic species by water removal, it is called nanopaper. Nanopapers are materials with exceptionally high mechanical properties in their own right and they can also be utilized as reinforcing phases in composite materials.

The influence of the basic properties within the nanopaper network has received surprisingly little attention. In this work, the tensile properties of BC nanopaper were examined as a function of the amount of material in the sheet, that is, by varying the nanopaper grammage. We observe that there exists a minimum threshold grammage, whereby the nanopapers possess sufficient mechanical strength. This elucidates the transition from a loose nanofibrous network to nanopapers, i.e., the point where nanopaper starts to be regarded as paper and not just a random agglomerate of nanofibres. In addition to analysis of the tensile properties, mercury intrusion porosimetry and helium pycnometry were applied to attain data for quantitative assessment of the correlation between the film structure and mechanical integrity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellulose nanofibres (CNF) are popular building blocks for a range of topical materials, including biodegradable nanocomposites, flexible substrates for electronics, and biomedical scaffolds. They can also be utilized in papermaking instead of conventional pulp fibres that are generally 3-4 orders of magnitude larger in width. The resulting paper from CNFs is called nanopaper, a substrate with exceptional mechanical properties [1,2] and promising potential for, e.g., membrane applications [3,4].

In traditional papermaking, grammage (mass per area) is one of the most important parameters that influence the strength properties of a paper sheet. Grammage is easy to control just by tuning the consistency of fibres during the papermaking process. Despite its importance, the development of nanopaper strength as a function of its grammage has not been reported previously. In this study, we introduce a systematic approach probing the effect of grammage on various mechanical properties of nanopaper. For CNFs, we have applied bacterial cellulose (BC) nanofibres which are biosynthesized individually into an isotropic hydrogel without the need to isolate the CNFs from a fibre matrix as is the case with plant-based CNFs. The approach of probing the effect of grammage is relevant, both from the fundamental, physical perspective and on the practical side of affairs, particularly taking into account the relative ease with which grammage can be tuned. Since nanopapers can be utilized directly as scaffolds for composite engineering [5], the results serve their purpose also within the composite community.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

BC was kindly supplied by fzmb GmbH (Bad Langensalza, Germany) in wet pellicle form containing 92 wt.-% water.

2.1 Manufacturing of BC nanopapers

The BC pellicles were cut into small pieces (with a length of approximately 5 mm) and blended (Breville VBL065/01, Oldham, UK) with deionised water for 2 min to produce a homogeneous aqueous suspension with 0.1 wt.-% BC. A pre-determined amount of the suspension (the amount depending on the desired nanopaper grammage) was then vacuum-filtrated onto a cellulose filter paper (VWR 413, 5-13 μm pore size, Lutterworth, UK) using a funnel with a glass frit (Schott, porosity No. 1, Mainz, Germany). After filtration, the wet filter cake was detached from the filter paper and sandwiched between blotting papers (Whatman 3MM Chr, VWR, Lutterworth, UK) and wet-pressed under a weight of 10 kg for 10 min to absorb the excess water. After this, the wet filter cakes were dried and consolidated in a hot-press (25-12-2H, Carver Inc., Wabash, USA) under a compression weight of 1 t for 4 h at 120 °C, sandwiched between fresh blotting papers and metal plates. The hot pressing is known to prevent the shrinkage of nanopapers and increase the density of the sheets, resulting in better mechanical properties of the papers.[6]

2.2 Characterization of BC nanopapers

2.2.1 Morphology

Morphology of the nanopapers was characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). SEM was performed using a high-resolution field emission gun SEM (LEO Gemini 1525 FEG-SEM, Leo Electron Microscopy Ltd., Cambridge, UK) at an acceleration voltage of 5 kV. Prior to SEM, the BC samples were attached onto carbon tabs stuck on the SEM stub and coated with Cr (K550 sputter coater, Emitech Ltd., Ashford, Kent, UK) for 2 min at 20 mA.

2.2.2 Grammage and thickness

The grammage of BC nanopapers was determined as the ratio between the weight and dimensional area of the nanopapers. The thickness of a paper was measured using a digital micrometer (705-1229, RS components, Corby, UK). The presented thickness values are an average of at least five parallel measurements taken from each nanopaper.

2.2.3 Density

Skeletal density values of the BC nanopapers were determined with helium pycnometer (AccuPyc 1330, Micromeritics Ltd., Dunstable, UK). The samples were weighed prior to placing them in the

measurement chamber. During pycnometer analysis, the chamber (containing the sample) is first pressurized with He up to a certain limit and then released allowing the pressure to decrease to a steady-state value by allowing the surplus He from the sample chamber to enter a separate expansion volume chamber. With the mass of the sample known, the density ρ_m of the sample can then be calculated using the equation

$$\rho_m = \frac{m_s}{V_C \frac{P_1}{P_2} \frac{V_E}{P_2^{-1}}} \quad (1)$$

where m_s is the mass of the sample, V_C is the volume of the chamber, V_E is the expansion volume of He, P_1 and P_2 are the elevated pressure and steady-state pressure in the chamber, respectively.

2.2.4 Porosity

Porosity of the nanopapers was determined by mercury intrusion porosimetry (AutoPore IV 9500, Micromeritics, USA).

2.2.5 Tensile properties

Tensile behaviour of the BC nanopapers was studied by two different methods: conventional tensile testing and with zero-span test typically used in paper testing.

For tensile testing the nanopapers were cut into dog bone shape specimens using a Zwick cutter. The test specimen possesses an overall length of 35 mm and the narrowest part of the specimen is 2 mm. Prior to the test, the specimens were secured onto testing cards using cyanoacrylate based adhesive (Everbuild Stick 2 superglue), in order to prevent the clamp of the tensile testing equipment from damaging the test specimens. Tensile tests were conducted using a Deben MICROTTEST tensile stage (Deben UK Ltd., Suffolk, UK), using a load cell of 5 kN and crosshead speed of 0.5 mm min⁻¹. A total of three specimens were tested and averaged for each type of sample.

Dry zero-span tensile strengths were determined according to the standard ISO 15361:2000.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphology of the BC nanopapers was studied using SEM (Fig. 1). Fibrous structure of BC with dimensions of approximately 50 nm in diameter is detectable but slightly less distinct in the compressed nanopaper compared to BC suspension before the nanopaper preparation. Hot-pressing of the nanopaper seem to have resulted in coalescence into bundles of BC fibrils. The morphology was independent on the grammage of the BC nanopaper.

Figure 1. Scheme of BC nanopaper manufacture, including scanning electron microscopy images of BC suspension dried in air and BC filtrated and pressed into nanopaper.

Figure 2. Thickness as a function of grammage of BC nanopaper.

For the range of grammages of the nanopapers studied (~ 5 - 100 g m^{-2}), the thickness increased approximately linearly with grammage of the nanopaper (Fig. 2). Similar trend has been reported previously [4].

Density of the BC in the nanopapers as measured with helium pycnometer was ~ 1.4 - 1.6 g cm^{-3} (Fig. 3), being in good agreement with the density values reported in literature for cellulose [7]. According to mercury intrusion porosimetry, porosity of the BC nanopapers was $72.57 \pm 9.42\%$.

Figure 3. Skeletal density as a function of grammage of BC nanopaper.

Representative stress-strain curves of BC nanopapers and the corresponding values of the tensile properties are presented in Fig. 4 and Table 1, respectively. The data indicates that the tensile properties do not correlate linearly with the grammage. Instead, there seems to be a threshold grammage between the 45 and 67 g m⁻², above which the tensile properties possess clearly increased mechanical strength. We believe that the minimum threshold grammage elucidates the transition from a loose nanofibrous network to nanopaper, i.e., the point where nanopaper starts to be regarded as paper instead of being just a random agglomerate of nanofibres.

Figure 4. Stress-strain curves of BC nanopapers of different grammages.

Grammage [g m ⁻²]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Young's modulus [GPa]
9	20.5 ± 7.7	7.6 ± 0.8
21	45.5 ± 4.2	11.8 ± 1.9
45	45.8 ± 4.0	9.7 ± 2.3
67	66.8 ± 9.2	30.1 ± 12.5

Table 1. Tensile strength and Young's modulus of BC nanopapers of different grammages.

Image of the fracture area of a BC nanopaper after tensile testing is presented in Fig. 5. According to the imaging, the nanofibrils appear to have come out as a whole from the network. This would be in contrast to the tensile behaviour of paper, where part of the fibres are known to break and part of them to come out as whole. Usually, a stronger network (via, e.g., beating) results in more broken fibres whereas stronger fibres and a weaker network lead to a higher number of pulled-out fibres. This is quite obvious: with stronger networks the fibre strength becomes a more dominant factor in tensile strength. Because the strength of an individual BC nanofibre is very high, it is conceivable that the strength of BC nanopaper may depend primarily on the strength between the fibrils.

Figure 5. Fracture area after tensile test of 45 g m^{-2} BC nanopaper imaged with scanning electron microscopy.

Zero-span strength has been used to complement the study of the tensile properties. With ordinary paper from pulp fibres, zero-span measurement gives information about the contribution of individual fibres on the strength of the paper, ignoring the influence of inter-fibrous bonding within the fibre network. The data, presented in Fig. 6, show that the contribution of individual nanofibres on tensile strength of paper increases linearly with the amount of the nanofibres included by the paper. The physical meaning of zero-span strength with BC nanopaper is unclear. That the zero-span index is not affected by the grammage, however, is not wholly unexpected since it may be indicative of the strength of an individual BC nanofibre.

Figure 6. (a) Zero-span strength and (b) zero-span index as a function of grammage of BC nanopaper. The average standard deviation of the zero-span strength index values is $0.015 \text{ kN m g}^{-1}$.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Vacuum-filtration and hot-pressing is a simple and efficient way to manufacture nanopaper out of BC nanofibres. The thickness and tensile properties of the BC nanopaper can be tuned by controlling the grammage of the nanopaper. There appears to be a minimum threshold grammage above which the nanopaper possesses sufficient mechanical strength, corresponding to the transition of the loose nanofibrous network into nanopaper. Due to the high strength of individual nanofibres, the failure of the nanopaper during tensile testing is seemingly caused by nanofibres being pulled-out rather than broken.

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